

MEDICINAL PROPERTIES OF GRAPES AND GRAPE JUICE

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Abstract. Grapes - the fruits of cultivated grapes and some other plants of the genus *Grapes*, in their mature form, which are sweet berries. A valuable food product and raw material for winemaking. Grapes are the first cultivated berry in the history of mankind, the love for which has not diminished over the past 8 thousand years. Grape juice has long been used for medicinal purposes, because this drink is just a storehouse of useful vitamins and minerals.

Keywords: grapes, healing properties of grapes, nutritional value, grape juice.

ЛЕЧЕБНЫЕ СВОЙСТВА ВИНОГРАДА И ВИНОГРАДНОГО СОКА

Аннотация. Виноград — плоды культурного винограда и некоторых других растений рода *Виноград*, в зрелом виде представляющие собой сладкие ягоды. Ценный пищевой продукт и сырье для виноделия. Виноград – первая окультуренная ягода в истории человечества, любовь к которой не уменьшается на протяжении последних 8 тысяч лет. Виноградный сок издавна используют в лечебных целях, ведь этот напиток просто кладезь полезных витаминов и микроэлементов.

Ключевые слова: виноград, целебные свойства винограда, пищевая ценность, виноградный сок.

INTRODUCTION

Sugar in grapes is found mainly in the form of glucose. One kilogram of grape berries, depending on the variety, the degree of ripening of the crop and the conditions for its cultivation, contains up to 300 or more grams of sugar. In addition, grapes also contain from 0.5 to 1.4% of tartaric, malic and other organic acids, 0.3-0.5% of minerals, in particular phosphorus, iron, calcium, etc., 0.15 - 0.9% proteins, 0.3-1% pectins, as well as vitamins A (carotene), B1 (thiamine, aneurin), B2 (riboflavin), C (ascorbic acid), B6 (pyridoxine), PP (niacin) and vitamin P.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Grapes are eaten fresh or dried into raisins (dried seedless grapes) or raisins and cinnamon (dried seedless grapes). Grapes are used in the production of wine. Compotes, juices, marinades and so on are also prepared from grapes. Used for decorative purposes.

Grape juice contains a large amount of glucose, fructose, which are easily absorbed by the body, potassium cations, organic acids, trace elements. The product is quite high-calorie (70-150 kcal / 100 g).

From grape juice, white, rose and red wines, brandy, as well as cognac spirit are obtained by alcoholic fermentation, which, after aging in oak barrels, is bottled under the brand name of cognac.

RESULTS

The benefits of grape juice

The pulp of grape berries contains mineral salts, vitamins A, C, PP, P, K, B vitamins, polyphenols, anthocyanins, biotin, pectin, potassium, magnesium, phosphorus. Doctors recommend drinking grape juice for diseases of the respiratory tract, cardiovascular system, anemia and migraines.

By regularly drinking grape juice, you:

- Reduce stress and strengthen the nervous system;
- Get rid of constipation;
- Slow down the aging process;
- Get rid of headaches;
- Prevent blood clots;
- Raise your hemoglobin level;
- Normalize pressure;
- Reduce your risk of cancer.

DISCUSSION

The use of grape juice has contraindications. Eating grapes and juice from it is not recommended for diabetes, stomach ulcers, cirrhosis of the liver, hypertension. With caution, you can drink grape juice for caries and diseases of the oral cavity.

CONCLUSIONS

Grape juice recipe at home. When choosing grapes for juice, give preference to whole bunches, not scattered berries. Easily crumbling fruits, most likely, have already begun to deteriorate. Grapes should not be wet and sticky, good berries are always elastic to the touch. It is desirable that the stalks are still greenish, and not withered. At the junction of the berries with a branch on the peel should not be muddy brown spots. Dark little spots on the berries are, on the contrary, a good sign, indicating maximum ripeness. Black grapes should not have green spots, and white grapes should have a yellowish tint, but not greenish.

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